

On P4-based Reliability: Path Protection for Programmable Data Planes

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Abstract—This paper proposes a purposely designed 1+1 "Protection Header" (PH) protocol, guaranteeing traffic is delivered between two remote endpoints with no perceived packet loss in case of failures in the intermediate network. The protocol defines an Ingress Switch (IS), identifying the traffic to be protected and cloning it over two link-disjoint working and backup routes. An Egress Switch (ES) receives the duplicates and forwards the first copy after stripping the protection information. We implemented the PH protocol on the Data Plane of SDN switches using the P4 programming language; then, we tested the protocol's operation on BMv2 switches in a virtual network. We showed that the proposed solution allows to successfully realise path protection between the source and the destination with no perceivable loss or delay in case of link failure.

Index Terms—reliability, p4, header, programmable data plane, SDN

I. INTRODUCTION

While stating a framework and the overall objectives for the future development of International Mobile Telecommunications (IMT) for 2020 and beyond [1], the ITU defined the concept *Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communication* (uRLLC). uRLLC requires five nines of reliability with user plane latency of 1 ms for payload sizes of 32 bytes. This "flash" requirement is paramount for the success of cloud services and virtual and augmented reality applications (an ever-growing trend as of 2022) to support future developments in health sectors, safety applications, entertainment, and other verticals.

Network devices have to cope with the stringent requirements of the aforementioned services. SDN has emerged as an effective tool to implement complex logic to manage the operation of network devices via software. Early iterations of SDN operate on the Control Plane of the devices, instructing how they should handle packet flows. On the other hand, Data Plane Programmability enhances the capabilities by altering how the packet switches handle packets at the silicon level; the designers can define new protocol headers and instruct how the switches should process each of their fields.

In this work we propose an overlay protocol allowing reliable communication in case of single-link failures along the network path. The "Protection Header" (PH) protocol fits in the ISO/OSI network stack between the Network (L3) and Transport (L4) layers, and it allows high-reliability communications over IPv4 domains via 1+1 path protection, accom-

plished by replicating the packets over link-disjoint traffic routes. The PH processing logic was implemented at the *Data Plane* of next-generation SDN switches by leveraging the P4 Programming Language; an SDN Controller establishes what packets should be protected and what are the correct routes for each communicating endpoints. The proposed solution was tested in a simulated virtual environment implemented in mininet to evaluate the system's reaction to link failures.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Paolucci et al. [2] discussed the features and the limitations of the P4 programming language as a new layer of softwarization to program the switches via a human-comprehensible API. The authors described the potential of data plane programmability for 5G Edge/Fog nodes, including dynamic traffic control for load balancing and offloading, latency-bounded service implementation, and novel stateful operations for embedded cybersecurity functions. They reckoned that the above will allow the next-generation infrastructure to adhere to strict latency, QoS and "flash" reaction requirements of 6G applications by responding to complex network events directly at the ASIC level.

Ramanathan et al. [3] proposed a 1+1 protection mechanism at the Ethernet layer for C-RAN functional split options on the front-haul by leveraging OpenFlow and Open vSwitch (OVS). The authors extended PRONet, a programmable optical software-defined network testbed, to offer 1+1 protection to meet the stringent network round-trip requirements imposed at the front-haul. However, the proposed approach did not leverage data plane programmability, so it could not extend the protocols supported by the switches, making their solution challenging to be adapted to different packet formats.

Lindner et al. [4] proposed the application of 1+1 protection for IP networks in P4. The authors defined a protocol called P4-PROTECT and tested it on BMv2 software switches and Tofino Edgework Wedge 100BF-32X switches. They adapted the MPLS protection specification in ITU-T G.7712/Y.1703 [5] to IP domains by creating an IP-over-IP backup tunnel. Packets on the working path were duplicated at network ingress over the secondary path, and replicas were identified using sequence numbers so that a single copy could be forwarded to the destination. Our project expanded on this one as IP-over-IP encapsulation was considered potentially

Fig. 1. High-level protected topology

harmful as it could lead to fragmentation, and unexpected drops, due to the substantial increase of the resulting protected packets.

III. PH PROTECTION FEATURES

Figure 1 shows the high-level topology considered when designing the PH protocol involves the following actors:

- the "Source" (src) and "Destination" (dst) nodes, respectively sending and receiving interesting traffic. These can be any entities exchanging unprotected IP packets, such as individual hosts or entire networks.
- the Ingress Switch (IS) is a P4 device duplicating the traffic and routing the copies via the "working" and the "backup" paths. The IS operates as a regular IP router if the traffic should not be protected. Otherwise, the IS adds a fixed-length PH header containing a clone identifier so that the ES can correctly detect the protected traffic.
- the Egress Switch (ES) is a P4 device sinking the traffic from both the working and the backup paths. The ES stores the clone identifiers of PH traffic seen in the past for the same protected pairs so that it can discard delayed duplicates and forward a single copy toward the destination node.
- the P4 SDN Controller populates the stateful match-action tables of the IS and ES switches; it does not take part in the network communications, and it could reside on a remote host (e.g. on the Cloud). The controller must synchronise the protected flow information between the IS and the ES to guarantee that both the switches align on the same pairs to be protected (they must be known in advance). Individually-protected flows are always assumed to be unidirectional.
- the "working" and "backup" paths are respectively the primary and the protection route between the source and the destination nodes. They have the IS and the ES as endpoints. The network provider should guarantee link-

disjointedness for the two paths; this requirement may not be guaranteed over the public Internet.

A. Protection Header Format

PH introduces a 48-bits header, injected between the IP packet header and the upper layer payload (e.g. the TCP or UDP). As such, intermediate devices not implementing the PH specification can simply disregard the header and continue forwarding the traffic to its intended destination. Figure 2 shows the structure of a PH header:

- the CLONE-ID (32 bits) field carries a unique sequence number for subsequent PH protocol data units. The IS and ES should know the same starting CLONE-ID once a new connection is established.
- the UPPER-PRT (8 bits) field indicates the protocol used in the PH payload. The values for various protocols are specified in RFC790 [7], and they duplicate the Protocol field of the protected IPv4 packet.
- the FLAGS (8-bit) are reserved for future extensions of the protocol.

Fig. 2. Protection Header fields

The PH protocol is uniquely identified by the yet-to-be-assigned *0xFA* (decimal 250) value in the IPv4 Protocol field. As such, all the packet switching hops in the working and the backup path should allow the PH protocol number to avoid accidental packet drops due to strict firewall mechanisms denying numbers not defined in the standard mentioned above.

B. CLONE-ID Acceptance

As the CLONE-ID field is a 32-bit value, a sequence number recycling mechanism is adopted to avoid overflows. PH relies on the same strategy described in [4] by allowing an identifier space spanning from 0 to $2^{32} - 1$ and defining a relational operator "less than or equal" (modulo 2^{32}) similar to RFC793 [8] and RFC1323 [9] for TCP Wrap-Around Sequence Numbers. The CLONE-ID of an incoming id_{inc} packet is considered successive to the expected id_{exp} one if and only if:

$$\begin{cases} id_{inc} - id_{exp} \leq \frac{MAX_{id}}{2}, & \text{if } id_{inc} \geq id_{exp} \\ id_{inc} - id_{exp} \geq \frac{MAX_{id}}{2}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The formula minimises the number of read accesses to the memory to one per packet. In case of failure of any link of the *working* path, or if one or more packets are lost in transmission on either of the two paths, the ES would not experience any interruption in the stream and continue updating its stored CLONE-ID.

C. Flow Identification

The IS must be made aware of what traffic has to be duplicated, while the ES must identify the traffic to be forwarded to the destination node after PH packets are received. In general, the PH switches require a mechanism to associate the packets with a flow to be protected. The logic should be consistent at both endpoints of the protected network.

PH identifies each protected pair with a tuple (source address, destination address). However, the protocol does not mandate how to construct the tuple. The algorithm used for building it defines the granularity of the protection. If, for instance, TCP traffic to Port 443 must be protected, the protected flow can be uniquely identified as (Source IP, A_{dst}) with $A_{dst} =$ (Destination IP, upper-protocol, destination port number).

We adopted the tuple (Source IP, Destination IP) to protect all the traffic between the two traffic endpoints. Furthermore, the switches must match the incoming traffic with individual register slots in memory containing the next expected CLONE-IDs. After exploring Bloom Filters [10] (deemed unsuitable due to the non-zero probability of identification collisions), the final implementation relied on the IS and ES having a table containing the entire list of fields used to identify the unidirectional flows. The switches identify a single "Connection ID" among 2^{32} possible values by using the specified fields as an index in a "Protected Connections" match-action table, as shown in Figure 3. The Connection ID is the slot index for the register storing the previously seen CLONE-IDs. The Controller populates the tables at the start time.

Fig. 3. Stateful table association between ingress fields and a connection identifier

D. Ingress and Egress Switches Operations

The IS receives traffic on its interface towards the source node, and it executes a lookup on its ingress match-action table to confirm if a datagram should be duplicated. The IS stores the last utilised sequence number for each protected pair in a memory register so that it can populate the CLONE-ID field with its successive values. The flows are always unidirectional, so return traffic should be associated with a different register slot. The IS executes the following operations whenever a packet arrives at its ingress interface:

- 1) If a protected flow exists, the IS increments the CLONE-ID by a unit, writes the new value in the PH header, and stores it in memory to be used for other packets in the same flow.
- 2) Otherwise, then there are two notable cases:
 - If the (source, destination) pair *should* be protected, the IS initialises a new CLONE-ID for the flow.

- Otherwise, the switch performs the regular (non-PH) routing operations.

The ES receives traffic on its network interfaces towards the working and backup paths; it analyses the IP header to confirm if the encapsulated protocol matches the protocol number associated with PH (0xFA). The ES discards any PH-encapsulated data units if they do not match any protected pair and there is no route for the traffic to be forwarded (i.e. the destination is behind a different ES). In case of no packet drops in the transport network, the ES should receive duplicate packets from both the working and the backup paths. The IS executes the following operations whenever a packet arrives at its ingress interfaces:

- 1) If a PH header is present when de-serialising the incoming packet, continue with the procedure; otherwise, process the packet as a regular IP packet.
- 2) The ES confirms if the (source, destination) pair has to be protected and the switch in question is the designated egress switch for the flow. If this is the case, continue with the procedure. Otherwise, if there is a route for the packet to the destination, forward the packet to the next hop.
- 3) Match the (source, destination) IP addresses of the packet with the register containing the last known CLONE-ID to identify a connection.
- 4) Confirm that the CLONE-ID in the PH in the received packet follows the currently stored one. If so, remove the PH and forward the packet via the interface towards the destination. Otherwise, drop it as a duplicate of an already-seen datagram.

Due to the PH protocol not relying on IP-over-IP encapsulation, if the destination network has more than one border gateway through which the traffic can arrive, all of them must be Egress Switches. They also must know the same flows and keep their CLONE-ID numbers updated during their operations, and CLONE-ID synchronisation must be guaranteed so that if a packet arrives at a switch, the others update their stored IDs accordingly. The procedure guarantees that PH effectively operates between stub networks.

IV. TESTS AND RESULT ANALYSIS

Figure 4 (a) describes the topology used for testing the PH protocol in a virtual environment using the emulator mininet [11]. The switches are running P4 Simple Switch targets into the BMv2 switches [12]. The intermediate switches act as regular IPv4 routers. ICMP Echo Requests were used to detect packet loss and unexpected duplication along the paths as they carry incrementing sequence numbers. In case of no failures, duplicated PH traffic carrying ICMP Echos arrives at the ES (S4 in the exhibit) successfully on both its ingress interfaces Eth-2 and Eth-3, as shown in Figure 5. The ES drops the second-arriving duplicate as it carries the same CLONE-ID while it forwards a single copy destination host.

In case of a single-link failure on the working path, the ES continues receiving copies via the backup. If link failure occurs

Fig. 4. PH testbench topology in case of no fault (a) and working path fault (b)

Figure 5 is a screenshot of a network traffic capture tool showing a list of packets. The table below represents the data shown in the screenshot:

Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Length	Protocol	Interface name	Info
1.0.0000..	10.0.1.100	10.0.2.100	IPv4	104	250	s4-eth3	Unknown (250)
2.0.0297..	10.0.1.100	10.0.2.100	IPv4	104	250	s4-eth2	Unknown (250)
3.0.0802..	10.0.1.100	10.0.2.100	IPv4	104	250	s4-eth3	Unknown (250)
4.0.0814..	10.0.1.100	10.0.2.100	IPv4	104	250	s4-eth2	Unknown (250)
5.1.0048..	10.0.1.100	10.0.2.100	IPv4	104	250	s4-eth3	Unknown (250)
6.1.0048..	10.0.1.100	10.0.2.100	IPv4	104	250	s4-eth2	Unknown (250)
7.2.9504..	10.0.1.100	10.0.2.100	IPv4	104	250	s4-eth3	Unknown (250)
8.2.9504..	10.0.1.100	10.0.2.100	IPv4	104	250	s4-eth2	Unknown (250)
9.3.9575..	10.0.1.100	10.0.2.100	IPv4	104	250	s4-eth2	Unknown (250)
10.3.9589..	10.0.1.100	10.0.2.100	IPv4	104	250	s4-eth3	Unknown (250)
11.27.125..	10.0.1.100	10.0.2.100	IPv4	104	250	s4-eth3	Unknown (250)
12.27.125..	10.0.1.100	10.0.2.100	IPv4	104	250	s4-eth2	Unknown (250)
13.28.144..	10.0.1.100	10.0.2.100	IPv4	104	250	s4-eth2	Unknown (250)
14.28.144..	10.0.1.100	10.0.2.100	IPv4	104	250	s4-eth3	Unknown (250)

Fig. 5. Duplicated packets at the ES; the PH Protocol Type (0xFA) and ingress interfaces are highlighted)

at more than one hop away from the IS, there is an "indirect" link failure as shown in Figure 4 (b). The IS continues forwarding traffic in both directions as the intermediate hops are unaware of the PH overlay, and no failure notification propagates back to the switch. The number of discarded packets would increase linearly with protected services.

Fig. 6. Number of protected flows at IS and ES in a no-fault (a) and faulty scenarios (b, c)

Figure 6 shows the expected number of flows between the IS and the ES when there are N protected paths in a no-fault scenario (a) and the case of a faulty working path (b and c). While the behaviour reduces the overall bandwidth efficiency of the system, the ES continues receiving copies of the traffic via the backup path with no perceivable packet loss or recovery delays at the destination node as PH guarantees that a packet clone is delivered via the backup path.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The project defined the new PH protocol enabling 1+1 protection by packet replication. It was implemented in the P4 programming language and tested on BMv2 P4 software switches running in a virtual environment. While the 1+1 strategy is usually applied at lower layers of the ISO/OSI protocol stack, the tests have been successful as packets get delivered from the traffic source to the destination with no perceivable loss or delay in case of link failures along the working path. However, the protocol might be further developed by defining a more efficient method to identify the protected packet flows by going beyond having a table storing all the matchable information, finding a synchronisation mechanism in case of redundant ISs and ESs in case the units have L2 or L3 reachability, addressing CLONE-ID desynchronisation at IS and ES, and extending the implementation to IPv6 while considering the existence of optional packet headers.

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